

Prabhakar Gajawada Bhagyamma Gajawada Satish Gajawada Artificial Intelligence Algorithm (PBGSGAIA)

Satish Gajawada
IIT Roorkee Alumnus
satish.gajawada.iit@gmail.com

Abstract—Many Human Swarm Optimization (HSO) algorithms were proposed in literature. These algorithms are based on Humans in general. But every Human is unique. Hence in this paper a novel algorithm based on 3 Humans Satish Gajawada, Prabhakar Gajawada and Bhagyamma Gajawada has been designed. Satish Gajawada is the son of Prabhakar Gajawada and Bhagyamma Gajawada. A unique algorithm titled Prabhakar Gajawada Bhagyamma Gajawada Satish Gajawada Artificial Intelligence Algorithm (PBGSGAIA) is proposed in this article.

Keywords—Artificial Intelligence, Swarm Intelligence, Human Swarm Optimization, Prabhakar Gajawada, Bhagyamma Gajawada, Satish Gajawada, Prabhakar Gajawada Bhagyamma Gajawada Satish Gajawada Artificial Intelligence Algorithm, PBGSGAIA

I. INTRODUCTION

Relevant Swarm Intelligence literature is shown in articles [1] to [6]. In this article, an interesting algorithm titled Prabhakar Gajawada Bhagyamma Gajawada Satish Gajawada Artificial Intelligence Algorithm (PBGSGAIA) has been designed. Section 2 explains proposed PBGSGAIA algorithm. Conclusions are made in Section 3 followed by references.

II. PRABHAKAR GAJAWADA BHAGYAMMA GAJAWADA SATISH GAJAWADA ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ALGORITHM

The Population is initialized in first 3 lines. Generation count is set to 0. Best individuals are found in lines 5 to 7. For each Satish Gajawada loop is started in line no. 8. Based on Random Number generated and probabilities, Satish Gajawada moves along Best Prabhakar Gajawada or Best Bhagyamma Gajawada or Best Satish Gajawada or along combination of three directions. Position update equations are shown in lines 13, 17, 21 and 27. Line no. 28 ends for each Satish Gajawada loop. Population is updated in lines 29 and 30. Generation count is incremented by 1. This process is continued until termination condition is reached in line no. 32.

Procedure: Prabhakar Gajawada Bhagyamma Gajawada Satish Gajawada Artificial Intelligence Algorithm (PBGSGAIA)

- 1) Initialize Prabhakar Gajawada Population
- 2) Initialize Bhagyamma Gajawada Population
- 3) Initialize Satish Gajawada Population
- 4) Set Generation = 0
- 5) Identify Best Prabhakar Gajawada with best fitness value
- 6) Identify Best Bhagyamma Gajawada with best fitness value
- 7) Identify Best Satish Gajawada with best fitness value

- 8) Loop for each Satish Gajawada:
- 9) Generate Random number "R"
- 10) if $0 < R < 0.25$:
- 11) Direction = Best Prabhakar Gajawada – Satish Gajawada
- 12) Convert Direction into Unit Vector
- 13) position = position + Direction*Step
- 14) if $0.25 < R < 0.50$:
- 15) Direction = Best Bhagyamma Gajawada – Satish Gajawada
- 16) Convert Direction into Unit Vector
- 17) position = position + Direction*Step
- 18) if $0.50 < R < 0.75$:
- 19) Direction = Best Satish Gajawada – Satish Gajawada
- 20) Convert Direction into Unit Vector
- 21) position = position + Direction*Step
- 22) if $0.75 < R < 1$:
- 23) Direction1 = Best Prabhakar Gajawada – Satish Gajawada
- 24) Direction2 = Best Bhagyamma Gajawada – Satish Gajawada
- 25) Direction3 = Best Satish Gajawada – Satish Gajawada
- 26) Convert Direction1, Direction2 and Direction3 into Unit Vectors
- 27) position = position + $0.33*Direction1*Step + 0.33*Direction2*Step + 0.34*Direction3*Step$
- 28) End for each Satish Gajawada loop
- 29) Update Prabhakar Gajawada Population
- 30) Update Bhagyamma Gajawada Population
- 31) Generation = Generation + 1
- 32) Loop until termination condition reached is true

III. CONCLUSIONS

An innovative algorithm which is based on 3 Humans Prabhakar Gajawada, Bhagyamma Gajawada and Satish Gajawada is invented in this article. Satish Gajawada moves along the direction of Best Prabhakar Gajawada or Best Bhagyamma Gajawada or Best Satish Gajawada or combination of these three directions. PBGSGAIA algorithm proposed in this article is just the beginning. One may move in the direction shown in this article to design more unique, interesting and innovative algorithms.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chao WANG, Shuyuan ZHANG, Tianhang MA, Yuetong XIAO, Michael Zhiqiang CHEN, Lei WANG, Swarm intelligence: A survey of model classification and applications, Chinese Journal of Aeronautics, Volume 38, Issue 3, 2025, 102982, ISSN 1000-9361, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cja.2024.03.019>, (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1000936124000931>)
- [2] Swarm Intelligence Algorithms for Optimization Problems a Survey of Recent Advances and Applications. Smita Samrat Mande,

Srinivasulu M, Sruthi Anand, Anuradha K, Mohit Tiwari and Esakkiammal U. ITM Web Conf., 76 (2025) 05008 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1051/itmconf/20257605008>

- [3] Sanjay M P , S.Keerthi , Vignesh D , Krupashree.B, 2015, Survey Paper on Swarm Intelligence, INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY (IJERT) NCAISE – 2015 (Volume 3 – Issue 21).
- [4] Chandrashekar Muniyappa and Eunjin Kim. 2025. Survey of Swarm Intelligence Approaches to Search Documents Based On Semantic Similarity. Proceedings of the 2025 4th International Conference on Cyber Security, Artificial Intelligence and the Digital Economy. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 705–710. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3729706.3729817>
- [5] Sun, W., Tang, M., Zhang, L., Huo, Z., & Shu, L. (2020). A Survey of Using Swarm Intelligence Algorithms in IoT. *Sensors*, 20(5), 1420. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20051420>
- [6] J. Tang, G. Liu, and Q. T. Pan, "A Review on Representative Swarm Intelligence Algorithms for Solving Optimization Problems: Applications and Trends," *IEEE/CAA J. Autom. Sinica*, vol. 8, no. 10, pp. 1627-1643, Oct. 2021. doi: 10.1109/JAS.2021.1004129